

The Cyrtarachninae genera of South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: Cyrtarachninae is a subfamily of orb-weavers of the family Araneidae represented by two tribes. It is considered one of the most specialised lineages of orb-weavers, and seven genera and 13 species are currently recorded from South Africa. In the tribe Cyrtarachnini, a reduced-web lineage is evident, represented by a strong visual masquerade, as seen in the following genera in South Africa: *Aethriscus* Pocock, 1902; *Cyrtarachne* Thorell, 1868; *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867 and *Pasilobus* Simon, 1895. In the tribe Mastophorini, the orb-web is abandoned entirely, and three genera are recorded from South Africa: *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910; *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895 and *Pycnacantha* (Fabricius, 1781). The 13 species recorded from South Africa are illustrated and discussed.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, Cyrtarachnini, Mastophorini, spanning-web, South African National Survey of Arachnida, taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), spiders have been widely sampled over the years, and several Cyrtarachninae genera have been recorded. Cyrtarachninae is a subfamily of orb-weaver spiders of the family Araneidae (Scharff & Coddington, 1997). It is considered one of the most specialised lineages of orb-weavers, with significant modifications to prey capture that frequently target moths. This involved moth specialisation, unusual web architecture, and strong use of masquerade and chemical deception. It was first established by Simon (1892) as Cyrtarachneae and has since been treated at taxonomic ranks such as tribes or subfamilies (Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014).

SUBFAMILY CYRTARACHNINAE

Common morphological traits of these spiders include large abdomens in adult females, often overhanging the cephalothorax, and elongated, strong legs used for prey capture. There is strong sexual size dimorphism, with the male being much smaller and of a different shape. The key defining behaviour of Cyrtarachninae are:

a. Web reduction in prey capture: Unlike typical orb-weavers, some Cyrtarachninae build highly reduced webs with few capture threads known as “spanning-thread” webs (Stowe, 1986). It consists of reduced capture spirals of which the threads are widely spaced, with large aggregate glue droplets relative to those of typical orb-weavers (Figs 9–11). However, some species do not use a web at all; instead, they capture prey with a bola consisting of a single silk line with a sticky droplet (Figs 42 & 54). While a few species are completely webless, hanging with spread out legs to grab prey flying past (Figs 75 & 76).

b. Moth specialisation and chemical mimicry: Many members are moth specialists, overcoming moths’ anti-adhesive wing scales by producing exceptionally sticky aggregate silk that attaches to moth scales (Eberhard, 1977). In some species, the spider emits female moth sex pheromones, sometimes multiple compounds simultaneously, actively luring prey directly into striking range.

c. Masquerade (visual mimicry of objects): Cyrtarachninae are classic examples of masquerade, where the adult females often resemble bird droppings, snails, seeds, or other inanimate objects. This allows them to remain exposed on vegetation during the day without danger of being attacked.

Molecular phylogenetic work shows that Cyrtarachninae split into two major evolutionary clades. Together, they form one of the most striking examples of adaptive radiation within orb-weaving spiders.

SUBFAMILY CYRTARACHNINAE

Tribe Cyrtarachnini

1. *Cyrtarachne* Thorell, 1868

C. ixoides (Simon, 1870)
C. finniganae Lessert, 1936
C. termitophila Lawrence, 1952

2. *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867

P. thorntoni (Blackwall, 1865)
P. walleri (Blackwall, 1865)

3. *Pasilobus* Simon, 1895

P. dippenaarae Roff & Haddad, 2015

4. *Aethriscus* Pocock, 1902

A. olivaceus Pocock, 1902
A. pani Lessert, 1930

Tribe Mastophorini

1. *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895

C. akermani Hewitt, 1923
C. debeeri Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004
C. longipes (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877)

2. *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910

A. seydeli Giltay, 1935

3. *Pycnacantha* Blackwall, 1865

P. tribulus (Fabricius, 1781)

I. TRIBE CYRTARACHNINI

Cyrtarachnini is one of the principal groupings within Cyrtarachninae, especially in narrower taxonomic treatments. These spiders typically retain some form of reduced web or triangular webs but do not use bolas. They are not known to rely strongly on pheromone mimicry. In South Africa they show strong visual masquerade, particularly insect or bird-dropping mimicry. Four genera meet the requirement of Cyrtarachnini: *Cyrtarachne* (Fig. 1); *Paraplectana* (Fig. 2); *Pasilobus* (Fig. 3) and *Aethriscus* (Fig. 4).

Figures 1–4. Cyrtarachninae, tribe Cyrtarachnini. 1. *Cyrtarachne ixoides* (Allen Jones). 2. *Paraplectana thorntoni* (Les Oates). 3. *Pasilobus dippenaarae* (Steve Goodall). 4. *Aethriscus olicaceus* (Les Oates).

1. *Cyrtarachne* Thorell, 1868

Cyrtarachne Thorell, 1868 is represented by 56 species found worldwide (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They are found mainly in tropical and subtropical regions (Asia, Africa, and other warm areas). They typically live on plants in forests and humid environments.

The females are 5–8 mm long, while males are much smaller (2–3 mm). In females, the abdomen is shiny with a triangular shape. In males, the abdomen is smaller and darker in colour.

These spiders are mostly nocturnal. During the day, they are found on vegetation, resembling bird droppings. Their modified spanning-thread web is made in the vegetation. They prey on flying insects that get stuck to the loosely spun threads bearing adhesive glue droplets. The spider then pulls the prey toward itself like a fishing line. Three species are known from South Africa

Cyrtarachne ixoides (Simon, 1870) (Figs 5–12)

Cyrtarachne ixoides was described in 1870 by Simon as *Peltosoma ixoides*. It has a wide global distribution and has been recorded from the Mediterranean basin to Georgia, Madagascar and South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). In 2008, it was first recorded in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008) and is currently recorded across all provinces except the Northern Cape (Fig. 12).

The female abdomen is large, shiny, and triangular or dome-shaped, with a white anterior border (Fig. 5). Therefore, the species is commonly known as the white-banded bird-dropping spider. In the males, the abdomen is smaller and darker in colour (Fig. 6). They produce a spanning-web (Figs 7, 9–11). It is presently known from eight provinces in South Africa (Fig. 12) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a). The epigyne is egg-shaped (Fig. 8).

Figures 5–12. *Cyrtarachne ixoides*. 5. Female (Len de Beer). 6. Male. 7. Female ventral view (Allen Jones). 8. Epigyne (after Bosselaers, 2018). 9–11. Female with prey in spanning-web (Allen Jones). 12. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red spot as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black spot from SANSA database.

Cyrtarachne finniganae Lessert, 1936 (Figs 13–14)

The male (3 mm) (Fig. 13) was described from Mozambique and was recorded for the first time from Gauteng and Limpopo in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2026b) (Fig. 14). Little is known about their behaviour, and the female is still unknown.

Cyrtarachne termitophila Lawrence, 1952 (Figs 15–16)

The male (2 mm) (Fig. 15) was described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo and was recorded for the first time from Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal in South Africa in 2026 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2026a) (Fig. 16). Little is known about their behaviour and the female is still unknown.

2. *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867

Paraplectana Brito Capello was described in 1867 and currently includes 13 species from Africa and Asia (World Spider Catalog, 2026). The species are easy to recognise by their round, dome-shaped abdomen that nearly covers the carapace. The surface of the abdomen is smooth and shiny and decorated with very bright reds, oranges, pinks and yellow spots. Colour morphs are seen in both species. Currently, two species have been identified from South Africa, but more undescribed species have been noted (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022b; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

They build modified orb-webs called “spanning-thread webs,” which have been observed in South Africa for *P. thorntoni* (Du Preez & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2022) and *P. walleri* (Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2020). They are nocturnal, and during the day they remain on vegetation, relying on their resemblance to ladybird beetles to avoid detection by predators. Because of their appearance, they are commonly called “ladybird spider”. It is a good example of Batesian mimicry, as it mimics the bad-tasting ladybird beetles that predators, like birds avoid.

Paraplectana thorntoni (Blackwall, 1865) (Figs 17–23)

Paraplectana thorntoni (Blackwall, 1865) is an African endemic species described as *Eurysoma thorntoni* from Mozambique. The species is known from seven African countries (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022b). In South Africa, it is widely distributed in six provinces (Fig. 23).

The female is recognised by the red abdominal markings (Figs 17–19), but some specimens are also yellow (Fig. 20) or a mix. They construct a spanning-web (Figs 21 & 22) (Du Preez & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2022; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023). The male is still unknown.

Figures 17–23. *Paraplectana thorntoni*. 17. Female on a small silk disk on leaf (Kobie du Preez). 18. Female (Les Oates). 19. Female with the beetle they mimic (Susan Dippenaar). 20. A female with yellow markings (Jolandie Buck). 21–22. Female in spanning-web (Kobie du Preez). 23. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown with red dot as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black dot from SANSA database.

Paraplectana walleri (Blackwall, 1865) (Figs 24–30)

Paraplectana walleri is an African endemic described by Blackwall (1865) as *Eurysoma walleri* from Mozambique. The species is known from three African countries. In South Africa it has been recorded mainly from the eastern parts of South Africa: Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal and the Eastern Cape (Fig. 30).

The colour of the female varies from yellow (Figs 26 & 28), orange (Figs 24 & 25) to almost red (Fig. 27). They construct a spanning-web (Figs 28 & 29) as discussed by Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2020).

Figures 24–30. *Paraplectana walleri*. 24–25. Female dorsal view and ventral view (Guy Johnston). 26. Anterior view (Paul van Rensburg). 27. Female dorsal view (Meg Cumming). 28–29. Female in spanning-web (Morah Cooper). 30. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown with red dot as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black dot from SANSA database.

3. *Pasilobus* Simon, 1895

Pasilobus Simon, 1895 was described in 1895, and is currently known from 14 species recorded from Africa, South and Southeast Asia and parts of Australasia (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They are recognized by their mottled, shiny triangular shaped abdomens.

Pasilobus is best known for its radically modified prey-capture web. The web is triangular, not circular, and consists of three framework radii: a central midline thread and widely spaced spanning threads hanging from it. These threads hang down like loose lines or strands with sticky droplets.

Pasilobus dippenarae Roff & Haddad, 2015 (Figs 31–35)

Pasilobus dippenarae is endemic to KwaZulu-Natal described in 2015 from Hilton. The female's carapace is partially hidden under the flattened, triangular-shaped abdomen (Figs 31–33). The abdomen is broad, often twice as wide as long, with low tubercles or

lobes. Legs are slender and relatively long, and the anterior pair is folded sideways (Fig. 32). Roff & Haddad (2015) described the species and discussed their general behaviour (Fig. 34). The species have been sampled from several localities around Pietermaritzburg, Kloof and Durban (Fig. 34).

Figures 31–35. *Pasilobus dippenarae*. 31–32. Female dorsal view (Steve Goodall). 33. Orange colour variant (John Roff). 34. The egg sac (John Roff). 35. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black.

4. *Aethriscus* Pocock, 1902

Aethriscus Pocock (1902) is endemic to Africa, and known from two species (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They are rare spiders, and both species are known from South Africa. Apparently, *Aethriscus* is one of the least understood species in the Cyrtarachninae group.

They build a very reduced spanning-thread web. The web has few sticky threads designed for intercepting flying prey, mainly moths. They are nocturnal and, during the day, sit exposed on vegetation, blending in and resembling a bird dropping.

Aethriscus olivaceus Pocock, 1902 (Figs 36–38)

Aethriscus olivaceus is an African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of Congo by Pocock (1902). The body has a triangular shape. The abdomen is dark with humps; the posterior area has a white triangular patch. Legs short, folded around the body. Little is known about their behaviour. When not active, they rest on vegetation and resemble bird droppings (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a). They have been recorded from the Eastern Cape, Gauteng, Limpopo, Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 38).

Figures 36–38. *Aethriscus olivaceus*. 36. Female dorsal view (Les Oates). 37. Female (Nicky Scott). 38. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black.

Aethriscus pani Lessert, 1930 (Figs 39-40)

40

Aethriscus pani is a rare African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of Congo by Lessert (1930). It was recorded for the first time from South Africa in 2026. The female is tawny, smooth and shiny, and the abdomen is twice as wide as it is long, and the legs are the same colour as the carapace (Leroy *et al.*, 2026). Little is known about their behaviour.

Figures 39–40. *Aethriscus pani*. 39. Female (Sharpview). 40. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black.

II. TRIBE MASTOPHORINI (Figs 41–43)

Mastophorini refers to a group of spiders that have abandoned the orb-web entirely. This includes cases where females use a bola or hang from a thread, grabbing prey as it flies past. These spiders possibly emit female moth sex pheromones, sometimes multiple compounds simultaneously, actively luring prey directly into striking range.

In South Africa, the tribe is represented by *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910 (1 sp.), *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895 (3 spp.) and *Pycnacantha* Blackwall, 1865 (1 sp.). *Pycnacantha* is listed here in the tribe Mastophorini. It meets the requirement of the tribe, namely the absence of a web.

Figures 41–43. 41. Female *Acantharachne* (Peter Webb). 42. Female *Cladomelea* with bolas (Len de Beer). 43. Female *Pycnacantha* (Les Oates).

1. *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910

The genus *Acantharachne* was erected by Tullgren in 1910 for the species *Acantharachne cornuta* from Tanzania. The genus is represented by eight species and is known only from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2026). Members of *Acantharachne* received little to no attention since their description, and unfortunately, little is known about their behaviour. Because they are so rare the genus was not included in the phylogenetic study of the orb-weaving spider family Araneidae (Scharff *et al.*, 2020).

Emerit (2000) suggested that the Malagasy species may use a bolas to forage, although there are no direct observations supporting this implied hunting strategy. Only one species is known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022c).

Acantharachne seydeli Giltay, 1935 (Figs 44–50)

Acantharachne seydeli was described by Giltay, 1935 from the Democratic Republic of Congo. It was first recorded in South Africa by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2022c). The female has a large, globular abdomen relative to the carapace. The carapace is broader than long and mottled (cream to brown with darker markings), bearing small tubercles (Fig. 44).

The abdomen has two large circular dorsal humps on the lateral edge. The humps have numerous blunt tubercles dorsally (Figs 45–47). Front legs are slightly longer and folded forward in front of the chelicerae when resting. Overall appearance resembles bird droppings, a form of defensive mimicry. The specimens sampled rest on the upper surfaces of leaves, while a female from Limpopo was collected during fogging of the savannah trees.

Figures 44–50. *Acantharachne seydeli*. 44–45. Female from Kloof (Andrea Sander). 46. Female from Gauteng (Nicky Scott). 47. Line drawing after Giltray (1935). 48–49. Female from Wakefield (Peter Webb). 50. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as downloaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSa database in black.

2. *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895

Cladomelea Simon, 1895, are endemic to the Afrotropical Region, and three of the four species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They have a highly derived hunting method using bolas. The females are broad-bodied with round abdomens, and the carapace features long, horn-like outgrowths (Fig. 66). Sexual dimorphism with males differing in shape and size (Fig. 70).

Cladomelea akermani Hewitt, 1923 (Figs 51–58)

Cladomelea akermani is a KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Hewitt (1923) from Pietermaritzburg, based on a female. The male was described by Leroy *et al.* (1998). Female with body and legs yellow-brown (Figs 51–53). Carapace hirsute, with three long, sharp-tipped tubercles (Fig. 55). Abdomen with rows of small tubercles each bearing tufts of setae (Fig. 55). Front legs long and densely covered with long, thin setae (Fig. 51). Male very small (Fig. 52, see arrow) with body and legs chestnut brown.

The females do not build an orb-web. Instead, they use a highly specialized hunting strategy swinging sticky silk droplet to capture flying insects, usually moths. Many species attract moths using chemical mimicry (Eberhard, 1977). This web reduction is accompanied by highly adhesive silk used on the bolas.

The spider constructs a reduced orb-web consisting of a bolas line used to catch moths at night. Several people have reported on their behaviour (Akerman, 1923; Leroy *et al.*, 1998). Diaz & Roff (2022) observed that *C. akermani* actively spins its body while swinging the bolas. They found that when activity occurs in an open environment, it creates turbulent air, spreading pheromones farther and creating a pocket of pheromones. They are found towards the end of the summer and into autumn. The egg sacs are attached to grass stems (Fig. 53) (Leroy *et al.*, 1998).

Figures 51–58. *Cladomelea akermani*. 51. Female dorsal view. 52. Female with very small male (See arrow). 53. Female with egg sacs. 54. Female with bolas. 55. Female colour variant. 56. Epigyne. 57. Male. 58. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSa database in black. Credits: 51–54. John Roff. 55. Sunčana Bradley. 56–57. After Leroy *et al.* (1998).

Cladomelea debeeri Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004 (Figs 59–64)

Cladomelea debeeri is endemic to South Africa. The female carapace is yellowish-brown, decorated with dark brown patterns and covered with long, white, woolly setae. Abdomen is fawn triangular, with an intricate pattern, each corner studded with five prominent tubercles (Figs 59–60); each tubercle bearing a tuft of long white setae (Fig. 61). Legs creamish brown with dark spiralling bands; legs without strong setae but bearing dense long, hair-like setae (Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

The bolas-line consisted of a three-strand thread held together with three droplets, positioned one above the other. Each droplet was approximately 2–3 mm in diameter. The spider used its fourth leg to hold onto a trapeze-line. The bolas-line was then whirled at intervals, using the second pair of legs. Initially, the whirling happened at intervals of about five minutes, but later became more frequent,

Figures 59–64. *Cladomelea debeeri*. 59. Female. 60–61. Female showing the abdominal pattern. 62. Female preparing the bolas. 63. Epigyne. 64. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSa database in black. Credits: 59. Sunčana Bradley. 60–61. John Roff. 62. Len de Beer.

Cladomelea longipes (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) (Figs 65–73)

A female of *C. longipes* was described by O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877 from the Democratic Republic of Congo. It is known from several African countries. It was first recorded in South Africa by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019) while Dippenaar-Schoeman & Odendaal (2020) provided more information on the very small, dark male (Figs 70–71). The female abdomen is triangular, dorsally pink, and infused with a grey guanophore and silky hair. Two large, yellow, and round tubercles are present on the antero-lateral corners of the abdomen, and four smaller white, round tubercles are arranged in rows between small white tubercles (Figs 65–66).

They make a bolas and swing it around (Fig. 67). During the observation period, only moths were caught. While observing the female feeding on a moth another moth landed on them. An indication that it possibly been attracted by pheromones of the captured moth or false pheromone of the spider (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Odendaal, 2020). The egg cocoon differ from that of other known *Cladomelea* species (Fig. 69).

Figures 65–72. *Cladomelea longipes*. 66. Female dorsal view. 66. Female showing the long tubercles on the carapace. 67. Female with bolas. 68. Epigyne. 69. Female with egg sac. 70. Female with small male. 71. Male. 72. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black. Credits: 65. Meg Cumming. 66-67, 69, 70-71, 69. Tinus Odendaal.

3. Pycnacantha Blackwall, 1865

An African genus described by Blackwall (1865) and represented by four species from Cameroon, Madagascar, Mozambique, Namibia, and South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). Meise (1932), who reviewed the genus and described two species, noted that the female of *Pycnacantha* resemble the fruit of *Tribulus terrestris*, an annual plant in the caltrop family (Zygophyllaceae) known for its strong spikes. They are also known as hedgehog spiders.

***Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) (Figs 74–80)**

The female *P. tribulus* are found in grasses and low vegetation (Fig. 73). Their spiky bodies and colouration allow the spiders to blend in with grass, particularly *Themeda* and *Cymbopogon* species that have spiky seeds. The spiders rest on the grass during the day and, in the evening, spin a triangular trapezium web between two adjacent grass stems. Here they hang upside down, with legs outstretched, trying to capture flying insects (Figs 74–76). These spiders are suspected of producing mimetic pheromones that attract male moths, which they grasp with their forelegs before feeding (Fig. 77). Egg sacs are attached to vegetation (Fig. 78) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 1996; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024). The species is widely distribution throughout South Africa (Fig. 79).

Figures 73–80. *Pycnacantha tribulus*. 73. Female. 74–76. Female hanging from a trapezium web with extended front legs waiting for prey. 77. Female with a moth. 78. Female with egg sac. 79. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black from SANSA database. Credits: 74. Allen Jones. 74–76. Peter Webb. 77–78. Les Oates.

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